

IMPROVING MECHANISMS OF CREATIVE SELF-DEVELOPMENT OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract: Teaching is a great art. This art is not easily, spontaneously achieved by an educator. Therefore, only those who have an air, passion, a quick and deep understanding of the requirements of the time, consistently increasing their scientific, socio-political level, pedagogical skills, carefully armed with the idea and ideology of independence, are able to achieve the teaching profession, that is, to become a true mentor for the healthy generation.

In this article, the issue of improving the mechanisms of creative self-development of future teachers is studied pedagogically.

Keywords: education, pedagogical skills, teacher, speech culture, self-development, ability, future teacher, innovation process.

The teaching profession has existed since ancient times as a special type of human activity. Because a person can continue and develop his life only because of education. A teacher (pedagogue) is a person who has special knowledge, professional training, and high moral qualities in educational institutions.

"Today, special attention is paid to the issue of self-development in the educational process, and the importance of the self-development system in training future specialists and improving their innovative competence is increasing. In particular, it is intended to define the priority directions of the reform of the higher education system, to raise the process of training highly qualified personnel with modern knowledge and high spiritual and moral qualities to a new level in terms of quality"[1] The legal framework is also aimed at improving the competence of the subjects of the educational process through self-development.

Implementation of the ideas of the "National Personnel Training Program", ensuring the success of reforms in the Republic's education system depends on the moral image and professional skills of teachers, trainers, and production masters working in educational institutions. It can be seen that every teacher, as specified in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education", has relevant knowledge in his subjects, high professional training and high moral qualities. should be. A training session organized by a teacher who has perfectly mastered the art of teaching is a means of imparting deep knowledge. serves as a mirror of what it is necessary to do to be a worthy citizen.

Currently, we can divide the professional requirements of a teacher into three main groups: general human characteristics, characteristics defining special aspects of the teacher's profession, special knowledge and skills in the subject. Psychologists refer to the group of pedagogical skills that reflect the synthesis of the mind, emotions and will of a person in justifying professional activity.

Pedagogical skills include didactic, planning, perspective-taking, quick results, communicative and organizational skills. At the same time, it includes universal human characteristics, spiritual-psychological, social-psychological, individual-psychological abilities, practical knowledge and skills, i.e. general pedagogical (informational, developmental), general labor (design, organization), independent organization. Learning (systematization and generalization of knowledge) features should be distinguished in the structure of the teacher's psychology. A teacher is not only a profession whose purpose is to convey knowledge, but also a person who performs an important and responsible task in forming a person as a person.

Among the professional requirements for future teachers, professional-pedagogical orientation occupies a special place. It embodies the main professional characteristics of a teacher. Professional directions of a teacher include interest in the teaching profession, pedagogical talent, and professional pedagogical enthusiasm. Interest in the teaching profession is considered the basis of pedagogical orientation, which is reflected in a positive attitude towards pedagogical activities, children, parents, and the desire to acquire pedagogical knowledge.

In modern psychological sources, there are a lot of opinions about the terms "self-assessment", "self-development", that is, the assessment of a person's abilities, qualities and place in society, professional advancement. It is not for nothing, of course, because in the era of rapidly developing globalization, the demands placed on human capital as a unique capital - the individual - are increasing.

"Self-awareness, self-awareness as a student, worker, teacher, engineer, etc., understanding of one's past and future, interaction with other people awareness of one's relationship, awareness of one's rights and duties, awareness of one's virtues and shortcomings, and the like, includes self-awareness. Due to self-awareness, a person can observe himself and learn about himself, understand his past experiences, and look at his actions with a critical eye. . A person's self-awareness and self-knowledge is a necessary condition for

managing his own behavior, for self-education and for developing his own mind" [2].

Self-development, taking into account the results of self-assessment, although it is a complex process, hard work, has its own advantages, and also serves as a guarantee of individual, personal development for the leader. In this case, the level of motivation, i.e., the need for personal and professional development, the level of enthusiasm, the dynamics of professional growth will increase, the effectiveness and efficiency of the activity will be ensured.

One of the important requirements for any teacher, especially a future teacher, is that he should have deep knowledge of the subjects he is teaching and should have mastered their methods. His deep knowledge of the subject and its theory, and his ability to convey it to the students in an interesting way increases the interest of children in this subject. Raises the teacher's reputation. Pupils not only appreciate the ability of the teacher to convey this knowledge to children, but also appreciate his interest in this subject and his dedication.

"The process of entering the teaching profession and acquiring pedagogic skills depends on whether he is able to enter the teaching team of the school and find his place in it. Not turning away from the support of the team, not losing heart when faced with difficulties, being able to see one's own mistakes and try to eliminate them is a sign of his formation as a teacher. At the same time, trying to educate yourself and work tirelessly on yourself is an integral part of professional qualities." [3, 45].

The famous pedagogue Jan Amos Comenius states that "Teaching is a very proud profession, higher than any other profession on earth." Describing the image of a teacher, he emphasizes the necessity of having the following qualities in his person: conscientious, hardworking, disciplined, moral, loves his work, treats students like their fathers, instills in them a desire for knowledge, 'a person who follows his students and has his own beliefs.

In order to improve the mechanisms of creative self-development of future teachers, as well as to carry out their professional activities, the following personal qualities are necessary: creativity, technical thinking, confidence in one's own strength, constantly improving one's professional skills, the ability to manage processes with emotional-firmness, the results of the emergence of professional competence are among them. Creative activity is a creative process that requires long-term preparation and skills. Creative activity is the basis of a person's long career, the source of all material and spiritual wealth. The level of formation of the main elements of human creativity and creative thinking has a

great impact on the development of the professional competence of future vocational education teachers and increases the productivity of teaching activities.

However, mastering the skills of professional activity is not only the integration of practical skills and competencies, the development of methods and tools for the effective organization of activities as a specialist, but also awareness of the methodology of professional creativity, the development of creative thinking and creative it requires adequate mastering of personal qualities of character. The formation of a creative person can be defined as the development of a person in terms of the creation of creative activities and creative products. The pace and scope of this process depends on biological and social factors, the activity and creative qualities of a person, as well as existing conditions, important vital and professional events.

Conclusion

Currently, science has collected a sufficient amount of real materials to penetrate into the essence of the process of self-development. The mechanism of self-development has the following characteristics: the future teacher chooses life goals and ideals according to social criteria, prepares himself for life in society, improves in collective activities to improve the world around him. There is a complex interrelationship and opposition between these factors of self-development and education: the purpose of life can be one, and the passion - in another area, resulting in the desire for self-improvement and the true self. inconsistency arises between self-discipline and so on. and contradictions cannot always be solved by the power of the student.

The indicated measures will increase the active role of telecommunications, computer and information technologies in the growth of the country's economy, ensure that people's activities and lives are equipped with the most modern types of technical devices and services, and enable the successful integration of the republic into world processes

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